

EFFECT OF FIBER LENGTH ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY ARRAYED CHOPPED STRANDS

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Keywords: Discontinuous fiber composite, stagger structure, fiber length, tensile strength, non-linearity

ABSTRACT

A sheet consisting of unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) with predetermined fiber length can be realised by cutting slits into prepreg at regular intervals in the fiber direction. UACS can be multidirectionally stacked and formed in complex shapes with minimal loss of mechanical properties compared to its original prepreg. This work aims to predict tensile strength of unidirectional composites with a stagger-structure of chopped strands made by regularly stacking UACS. The author has previously identified that final failure is caused by unstable growth of delamination from stress concentration at the tip of bundles through in-situ observation during tensile tests, and proposed an analytical equation to predict its strength using the interlaminar fracture toughness in Mode II. The equation showed good agreement with experiments in the case of relatively long fiber length, but could not explain a large knock down of tensile strength with decreasing fiber length in experiments. In the present study, a newly-revised equation utilizes the stress-strain curve's non-linearity to account for the effect of fiber length, relying on interlaminar shear yield stress obtained from compression interlaminar shear (CILS) tests, in addition to interlaminar fracture toughness in Mode II obtained by end-notched flexure (ENF) tests. It was confirmed that this closely reflects the relation between tensile strength and fiber length, without applying any fitting parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve a superior formability more similar to SMC (Sheet Molding Compound), applications for composites with dispersed predetermined pre-cut fiber bundle is a focus in the industry. The authors have proposed a sheet-like unidirectional material known as Unidirectionally Arrayed Chopped Strands (UACS) realized by inserting slits into a unidirectional prepreg at predetermined fiber lengths and intervals. It has been proven that this material significantly improves moduli and strengths and minimises their scatter compared to SMC [1-6]. Configuration of this laminated UACS material, aside from the scale effect replicates human bone and teeth structure as hard inorganic protein matrix plates are stacked alternately forming a similar staggered structure. This structure has both an ideal balance in strength and toughness at high level and has attracted attention in the biomimetics field [7]. The present study focuses on the behaviour of composite material made of discontinuous fiber bundles using unidirectional laminate of UACS, in particular to express a good relation with tensile strength and fiber length, intended to obtain guidelines for material design.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Preparation

Slits introduced in the prepreg at predetermined intervals with no overlapping slits were stacked

and prepared for a tensile test specimen. Specimens were made from a prepreg with T800S carbon fiber, #3900-2B epoxy resin with a fiber volume fraction of 56%. The specimen geometry and two sheet patterns a, b shown in Figure 1. Slits are inserted perpendicular to the fiber direction in only the centre section of the sheets with an interval of the fiber length l_b . These sheets are stacked alternately for a total of 8 plies and cured at 180°C for 2hrs, fabricating a staggered composite structure. From this flat composite plate, specimens were prepared with a width of 15mm in the 0 degree direction (slits are penetrated perpendicular to the specimen width direction). On each edge of the specimen, GFRP tabs are placed to acquire a span of 150mm in the centre section. After preparation of the specimen, tensile test was conducted at a crosshead speed of 2mm/min. The following 6 types of fiber lengths were prepared and tested in each N6; 6.35, 9.375, 12.5, 18.75, 25 and 50mm. As a control, tests for continuous fiber prepreg were also carried out in parallel.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry of $[a/b]_4$ laminate.

2.2 Results

Experimental results are summarised in Table 1 and Figure 2. As the fiber length l_b increases, both elastic modulus and strength also increase. The stress-strain curve for each fiber length is shown in Figure 7 (left). The strain was obtained by strain gauges glued on both surfaces, however since the slitted section on the surface locally deforms a lot, it is impossible to guarantee the strain value from the gauges over 0.2% strain. Therefore, strain in this range is obtained from a conversion of the displacement. Fracture specimens are shown in Figure 3 and it was observed that for fiber lengths at least under 18.75mm, final failures were all caused by delamination.

Bundle length l_b	mm	6.25	9.375	12.5	18.75	25	50	Cont.
Bundle thickness h_b	mm	0.191	0.190	0.192	0.190	0.193	0.193	0.191
Modulus (0.1-0.3%)	GPa	92.2 (3.4)	107.2 (3.1)	120.8 (2.5)	119.7 (4.9)	139.5 (6.2)	139.1 (1.2)	149.3 (1.8)
Strength	MPa	727 (15)	1053 (14)	1233 (12)	1482 (24)	1538 (67)	1609 (36)	2991 (28)
Strain to failure	%	0.75 (0.04)	0.93 (0.03)	0.90 (0.02)	1.14 (0.10)	0.97 (0.05)	0.97 (0.03)	1.77 (0.03)

(): Standard deviation

Table 1: Summary of experimental results.

Figure 2: Experimental results of tensile strength and modulus for different fiber length.

Figure 3: Fracture specimens after tensile tests.

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 Linear Model

In the previous study [1], it was verified for a unidirectional laminate of UACS, that prediction of tensile strength can be carried out by determining the stress of an unstable delamination growth from stress concentration at the slit opening of the outermost surface (tip of fiber bundle). This unstable growth connects to the adjacent slits, eventually leading to final failure. An analytical model is constructed and derived based on a conceptual diagram shown in Figure 4, where initiation of the delamination occurs from the tip of the fiber bundle in the outermost layer.

Figure 4: Schematic of analytical model.

A linear relationship is assumed between the composite stress σ_{LT} , composite strain ε_{LT} and modulus of the fiber bundle E_b .

$$\sigma_{LT} = E_b \varepsilon_{LT} \quad (1)$$

By zoning A and B as shown in Figure 4, the fiber bundle in zone A is completely delaminated and assumingly not subjected to any load. Since the remaining layers in zone A bear all the load, it is possible to deduce the strain energy U_A , U_B for zone A and B as expressed in equation (2) and (3).

$$U_A = \frac{P^2}{W^2(H-h_b)^2} \frac{1}{2E_b} W(H-h_b)a \quad (2)$$

$$U_B = \left(\frac{P}{HW}\right)^2 \frac{1}{2E_b} HW(L-a) \quad (3)$$

Where, H , W and h_b are specimen thickness, width and fiber bundle thickness respectively. The relation between load P is expressed in equation (4).

$$P = WH\sigma_{LT} \quad (4)$$

Strain energy release rate G for delamination growth is expressed in equation (5). This energy release rate does not contain the component of delamination growth length a and is therefore considered as an unstable growth. Accordingly the observed delamination tensile stress is a function of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc} as considered in equation (6)

$$G = \frac{1}{W} \left(\frac{dU_A}{da} + \frac{dU_B}{da} \right) = \frac{\sigma_{LT}^2 h_b}{2E_b} \frac{H}{H-h_b} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{LT-d} = \sqrt{\frac{2E_b G_{IIc}}{h_b} \left(1 - \frac{h_b}{H}\right)} \quad (6)$$

This linear model clearly demonstrates the impact of the fiber bundle thickness h_b and interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc} to the tensile strength σ_{LT-d} . However as shown in equation (5), the fiber length l_b is not included hence it is difficult to explain the dependency of tensile strength on fiber length with experimental results shown in 2.2.

3.2 Non-linear Model

The stress-strain curve shown in Figure 7 (left), presents no spike until final failure. Therefore, the assumption that final failure instantaneously caused by delamination can be justified. The non-linear nature of the stress-strain curve is taken into account to improve on the deduction of 3.1 and introduce the impact of fiber length l_b ,

To incorporate the factor of fiber length l_b in the modulus, a constant interlaminar shear stress τ in the fiber bundle is considered shown in Figure 5. This allows a linear expression for a stress recovery, in other words the stress recovery length δ can be expressed in equation (7).

$$\delta = \frac{\sigma_b h_b}{2\tau} \quad (7)$$

Figure 5: Assumption of stress distribution in fiber bundle length.

By assuming the composite fiber direction is under uniform strain ε_{LT} , the maximum fiber bundle stress σ_b and composite stress σ_{LT} can be expressed as equation (8) and (9). This assumption is based on an interpretation that the laminate is stacked with enough layers so that the slits are not overlapped with each other, while this differs from the exact experimental conditions. As the fiber length l_b decreases, the non-linearity of the stress-strain curve becomes greater as shown in equation (9).

$$\sigma_b = E_b \varepsilon_{LT} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{LT} = \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{l_b}\right) \sigma_b = \left(1 - \frac{h_b E_b \varepsilon_{LT}}{2l_b \tau}\right) E_b \varepsilon_{LT} \quad (9)$$

Tensile strength of the fiber bundle σ_{b-b} is used for the tensile strength σ_{LT-b} when the composite is fractured due to fiber breakage represented in equation (10).

$$\sigma_{LT-b} = \left(1 - \frac{h_b \sigma_{b-b}}{2l_b \tau}\right) \sigma_{b-b} \quad (10)$$

A strength prediction for the composite fracture by delamination is performed, using the conceptual diagram of Figure 4. Similar to 3.1, since the delaminated fiber bundle at the outermost layer is not subjected any load in zone A, the remaining layers carry the entire load, hence the strain ε'_{LT} in that zone is larger than the composite strain ε_{LT} . This difference in magnitude is larger for a non-linear stress-strain relation shown in equation (9) rather than the linear expression described in equation (1). ε'_{LT} can be deduced from equation (11) to (14).

$$\frac{H}{H - h_b} \sigma_{LT}(\varepsilon_{LT}) = \sigma_{LT}(\varepsilon'_{LT}) \quad (11)$$

$$\varepsilon'_{LT} = \varepsilon_{LT-p} \pm X \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{LT-p} = \frac{l_b \tau}{h_b E_b} \quad (13)$$

$$X \equiv \sqrt{\frac{H}{H - h_b} (\varepsilon_{LT-p} - \varepsilon_{LT})^2 - \frac{h_b}{H - h_b} \varepsilon_{LT-p}^2} \quad (14)$$

Here, ε_{LT-p} corresponds to strain when the stress recovery length reaches the entire length of the fiber bundle from equation (7) and (8), and since ε'_{LT} cannot exceed ε_{LT-p} , the two solution from equation (12) are automatically expressed as equation (15).

$$\varepsilon'_{LT} = \varepsilon_{LT-p} - X \quad (15)$$

Similar to 3.1, strain energy U_A and U_B in zone A and B become equation (16) and (17), and the strain energy release rate of delamination growth is deduced as equation (18).

$$U_A = (H - h_b) W a \int_0^{\varepsilon_{LT}} \sigma_{LT} d\varepsilon_{LT} \quad (16)$$

$$U_B = H W (L - a) \int_0^{\varepsilon_{LT}} \sigma_{LT} d\varepsilon_{LT} \quad (17)$$

$$J = \frac{1}{W} \left(\frac{dU_A}{da} + \frac{dU_B}{da} \right) = \frac{E_b}{6} \left[(H - h_b) \varepsilon_{LT-p}^2 \left(1 - \frac{X}{\varepsilon_{LT-p}} \right)^2 \left(2 + \frac{X}{\varepsilon_{LT-p}} \right) - H \varepsilon_{LT}^2 \left(3 - \frac{\varepsilon_{LT}}{\varepsilon_{LT-p}} \right) \right] \quad (18)$$

The factor of delamination growth length a is not included in equation (18) therefore considered as an unstable growth. Stress that initiates delamination from the tip of the fiber bundle becomes the tensile strength σ_{LT-d} as expressed in equation (19), where strain energy J is equivalent to the Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. The unknown composite strain ε_{LT-d} is numerically determined and substituted in the stress-strain relationship which is expressed in equation (20).

$$G_{IIc} = J(\varepsilon_{LT-d}) \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma_{LT-d} = \left(1 - \frac{h_b E_b \varepsilon_{LT-d}}{2l_b \tau}\right) E_b \varepsilon_{LT-d} \quad (20)$$

By approximating equation (18), it is possible to obtain an explicit solution of ε_{LT-d} (details are depicted in Appendix).

3.3 Results

In previous studies [8], the author performed a deduction up to 3.2, confirming tendency in reduction of tensile strength as the fiber length was shortened for unidirectional laminates of UACS made of CF/PP, PA6, PPS thermoplastic prepregs. However these results showed large experimental scatter due to complication in molding.

In the present study, as shown in 2.2, by establishing a consolidated thermoset prepreg molding method, it was sufficient to validate strength predictions with minimal scatter. In addition, interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc} and shear stress τ were evaluated by using standard test methods for strength predictions without fitting parameters. More specifically, G_{IIc} was measured according to End Notched Flexure test (JIS K7086) and τ evaluated by Compression Interlaminar Shear test (CILS) according to ASTM D3846 for a unidirectional prepreg without slits. The averages of both G_{IIc} and τ were used for analysis. The fiber bundle modulus E_b and strength σ_b obtained in 2.2 for a continuous prepreg were also used. These input parameters are obtained experimentally for the analysis, summarized in Table 2

Bundle modulus (0.1-0.3%) E_b GPa	149.3	(1.8)
Bundle strength σ_c MPa	2991	(28)
Interlaminar shear strength τ MPa	69.6	(2.2)
Interlaminar fracture toughness in mode II G_{IIc} J/m ²	2057	(107)

(): Standard deviation

Table 2: Inputs for analysis based on experimental results.

Analytical results with various models are given in Table 3. For fiber breakage at the fiber bundle, equation (10) was applied. And for delamination with a linear and non-linear stress-strain curve, equation (6) and (20) were applied respectively. The predicted strength significantly differs depending on the failure mechanism, either from a fiber breakage or from a delamination, and the latter showed closer correspondence to experimental results.

Bundle length l_b	mm	6.25	9.375	12.5	18.75	25	50
Bundle thickness h_b	mm	0.191	0.191	0.191	0.191	0.191	0.191
<i>Fiber breakage model</i>							
Strength	MPa	1026	1690	2003	2339	2496	2743
<i>Delamination, Linear model</i>							
Strength	MPa	1677	1683	1672	1681	1670	1668
<i>Delamination, Non-linear model</i>							
Modulus (0.1-0.3%)	GPa	129.7	136.3	139.5	142.8	144.4	146.8
Strength	MPa	896	1124	1242	1390	1450	1558
Strain to failure	%	0.82	0.95	1.00	1.05	1.06	1.09

Table 3: Summary of predictions with various models.

For the fiber breakage model (Equation 10), experimental results (2.2) were plotted against both predicted strengths for a linear expression (3.1) and non-linear expression (3.2) shown in Figure 6. For

the linear model, if the fiber length is long then the results show good agreement, however this prediction does not account for the dependency of fiber length. On the other hand, for a non-linear model the dependency on fiber length is incorporated hence quantitatively the results show good agreement.

By applying equation (9), a stress-strain curve for various fiber lengths are constructed and shown in Figure 7 (right). The experimental results shown in Figure 7 (left) presents a tendency that as the fiber length increases the modulus will also increase.

Figure 6: Comparison of experiment and prediction.

Figure 7: Comparison of stress-strain curves between experiment (left) and prediction (right).

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Failure Mechanisms

As shown in Figure 6, strength predictions for a delamination dominant non-linear model, presents

relatively good agreement with experimental values. However, observing the fractured specimens shown in Figure 3, specimens for fiber length l_b with 25mm and 50mm displayed a straight fracture surface perpendicular to the loading direction and a noticeable delamination was not observed. As the stacking sequence consists of two patterns of slits and the slitted location is overlapped for every second ply the fracture surface contains half of the continuous fibers. Assuming failure consists of half of the fibers, the strength should simply be half the strength of a continuously aligned prepreg, 2991MPa shown in Table 1. However, fiber length l_b for 25mm and 50mm displays strength greater than this approximation. The difference in strength between the two is 71MPa which is greater than the standard deviation of the strength scatter, thus it is adequate to assume there is a mechanism that contributes to the difference in strength. Assumed that delamination is initiated from the tip of the fiber bundle in the outermost layer, and at this instant the load sustained by delaminated fiber bundle is redistributed to other layers, making it possible that the remaining 7 layers can no longer bear the load, leading to fiber breakage. At this point where initiation of delamination determines the strength, there is a good reason the prediction meets experimental results even for fiber length 25mm and 50mm, as well as for results under 18.75mm.

4.2 Gap between Experiment and Analysis

As illustrated in Figure 6, strength predictions for a non-linear model dependent on delamination failure are lower than experimental values for a long fiber length range, and higher than ones for a short fiber length range. This variance in analytical results presumes to be due to the constant shear stress τ incorporated for any given fiber lengths. As mentioned previously, τ is determined from the interlaminar shear stress by the CILS test method. With this method, it is improbable to consider the CILS specimen fails under complete yield, and thus the method is most likely to underestimate the interlaminar shear stress. Therefore, for long fiber length which can bear high tensile load, a larger stress transfer between the fiber bundle, namely shear stress increases, so a larger τ is required. Conversely, for a short fiber length, a lower τ should be applied. By adjusting the interlaminar shear stress τ for relevant fiber length, the predicted strengths value should show good agreement with experimental results. The predicted stress-strain relationship shown in equation (9) can be optimized by fitting the unknown τ for relevant fiber lengths.

4.3 Stress-strain curves

Stress-strain curves obtained experimentally shown in Figure 7 (left) present a tendency of high modulus at high strain regions especially for long fibers. The non-linear elastic nature of carbon fiber itself (approximately for 1% strain increase, 20% increase in modulus) is the most likely the cause of this tendency. As the focus of this present study was to develop an analytical model for tensile strength predictions, the elastic modulus was considered to be constant which led to a difficulty in acquiring a precise quantitative stress-strain relation from this model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To validate the effect of the fiber length in a unidirectional fiber bundle with tensile strength, a reduction in tensile strength as the fiber length shortens was identified experimentally by use of a unidirectional laminate of UACS. On the other hand, by considering the non-linear nature of the stress-strain curve, an analytical model is proposed for tensile strength which takes into account the stress when the strain energy release rate of an unstable growth of delamination reaches the Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. This model well explained the experimental relation between tensile strength and fiber length, and quantitatively showed good agreement without applying any fitting parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper is based on results obtained from the project, “Advanced Materials & Process Development for Next-Generation Aircraft Structures” commissioned by the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO).

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APPENDIX

To obtain a positive $\varepsilon_{LT,d}$ solution, an approximation of equation (18) is conducted. Firstly, substitute X^2 component from equation (18) into equation (14) to leave the square root component.

$$\left[(3H - 2h)\varepsilon_{LT,p}^2 - H(\varepsilon_{LT,p} - \varepsilon_{LT})^2 \right] X = -H(\varepsilon_{LT,p} - \varepsilon_{LT})^3 + 3H\varepsilon_{LT,p}^2(\varepsilon_{LT,p} - \varepsilon_{LT}) - 2h\varepsilon_{LT,p}^3 - \frac{6\varepsilon_{LT,p}J}{E_b} \quad (21)$$

After squaring both sides, compile and define it as z shown in equation (22). Then, apply α defined in equation (24) to obtain the relation in equation (23).

$$z = \frac{\varepsilon_{LT}}{\varepsilon_{LT,p}} \quad (22)$$

$$z^6 - 6z^5 + 12z^4 + (4\alpha - 8)z^3 - 12\alpha z^2 + 8\alpha - 8 + 12\frac{h}{H} - 4\left(\frac{h}{H}\right)^2 - 4\frac{h}{H-h}\alpha^2 = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{h}{H} + \left(\frac{1}{h} - \frac{1}{H}\right) \frac{3J}{E_b \varepsilon_{LT,p}^2} \quad (24)$$

Since $0 < z < 1$, an approximation of 5th power and beyond can be disregarded, and therefore only one z_d solution can satisfy equation (23). β , γ and θ , defined in equation (26), (27) and (28) is applied to equation (25).

$$z_d = \frac{2-\alpha}{12} + \frac{\gamma}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(2-\alpha)^2}{12} + 2\alpha - \gamma^2 + \frac{(2-\alpha)(\alpha^2 + 32\alpha + 4)}{108\gamma}} \quad (25)$$

$$\beta = \frac{2}{3}(\alpha - 1) + \frac{h}{H} - \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{h}{H}\right)^2 - \frac{h}{3(H-h)}\alpha^2 \quad (26)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{(2-\alpha)^2}{36} + \frac{2\alpha}{3} + \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{\alpha^2 + 12\beta} \cos \theta} \quad (27)$$

$$\cos 3\theta = \frac{3\beta(\alpha^2 + 20\alpha + 4) - 2\alpha^3}{2(\alpha^2 + 12\beta)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (28)$$

Therefore, from equation (22) the failure strain $\varepsilon_{LT,d}$ can be expressed in equation (29), and this is substituted to equation (20) to obtain the tensile strength $\sigma_{LT,d}$.

$$\varepsilon_{LT,d} = z_d \varepsilon_{LT,p} \quad (29)$$

As z_d becomes closer to 1 the accuracy decreases from equation (22) and the analysis in section 3.3 showed an error range of within 4%.